

When accurate prediction models become harmful self-fulfilling prophecies

Wouter van Amsterdam*

*University Medical Center Utrecht, Utrecht, the Netherlands
University of Utrecht, Utrecht, the Netherlands*

W.A.C.VANAMSTERDAM-3@UMCUTRECHT.NL

Nan van Geloven

Leiden University Medical Center, Utrecht, the Netherlands

Jesse Krijthe

Delft University of Technology, Delft, the Netherlands

Rajesh Ranganath

New York University, New York City, USA

Giovanni Cinà*

*Amsterdam University Medical Center, Amsterdam, the Netherlands
University of Amsterdam, Amsterdam, the Netherlands
Pacmed, Amsterdam, the Netherlands*

G.CINA@AMSTERDAMUMC.NL

Abstract

Prediction models are popular in medical research and practice. By predicting an outcome of interest for specific patients, these models may help inform difficult treatment decisions, and are often hailed as the poster children for personalized, data-driven healthcare.

We show however, that using prediction models for decision making can lead to harmful decisions, even when the predictions exhibit good discrimination after deployment. These models are *harmful self-fulfilling prophecies*: their deployment harms a group of patients but the worse outcome of these patients does not invalidate the predictive power of the model. Our main result is a formal characterization of a set of such prediction models. Next we show that models that are well calibrated *before* and *after* deployment are useless for decision making as they made no change in the data distribution. These results point to the need to revise standard practices for validation, deployment and evaluation of prediction models that are used in medical decisions.

Keywords: Prediction models, Deployment, Monitoring, Causal Inference

1. Introduction

Clinicians and medical researchers are fond of outcome prediction models (OPMs): statistical models that predict a certain medical outcome based on patients' characteristics (Steyerberg, 2009). Researchers develop OPMs to provide information to clinicians so they may use this information in difficult treatment decisions (e.g. Salazar et al. (2011)). In some cases, clinicians will treat patients with a bad expected outcome more aggressively, for example by giving cholesterol lowering medication to patients with a high predicted risk of a heart attack (Arnett et al., 2019; Karmali et al., 2018). In other cases, for instance when the treatment is burdensome or scarcely available (e.g. ventilator machines on the intensive care during a pandemic), clinicians may reserve treatment for patients with a good predicted outcome.

Many such OPMs are added to the protocol of care by designing specific thresholds for specific actions (Arnett et al., 2019). If the predicted outcome is above or below the threshold a certain action is taken, e.g. the patient receives a more aggressive therapy. The basis for including an OPM in a care protocol is generally predictive accuracy in validation studies (Kattan et al., 2016). In these validation studies, the OPM may or may not have been used to inform treatment decisions.

* these authors contributed equally

Figure 1: Some outcome prediction models yield harmful self-fulfilling prophecies when used to guide treatment decisions, meaning the new policy harms a subgroup of patients but the prediction model displays good discrimination because these patients were already predicted to have worse outcomes. OPM: outcome prediction model.

At first, it may seem that this approach is beneficial since giving more information should lead to better treatment decisions. However, implementing a prediction model for treatment decisions is an intervention that changes treatment decisions and thus patient outcomes. Whether this change in treatment policy improves patient outcomes is not determined by prediction accuracy in a validation study (van Amsterdam et al., 2022). For instance, if a certain patient subpopulation historically received suboptimal care, an accurate OPM will predict a worse outcome for these patients compared to similar patients outside of the subpopulation. If clinicians would withhold effective treatments (e.g., due to scarcity) to this underserved subpopulation because the OPM predicted a bad outcome for them, implementing the OPM caused harm to these patients, despite being accurate. Moreover, the implementation of this harmful new policy brought about the scenario predicted by the OPM, as in a *self-fulfilling prophecy*.

In this article we address the following questions: 1) Under what conditions is a new policy based on a OPM going to be harmful, meaning that it leads to worse outcomes than before using the model? 2) In what circumstances can we detect that something has gone wrong via measures of discrimination or calibration? In what follows we provide a formalization of the case where patients with high predicted outcomes (i.e. above a fixed threshold) get treatment, working under the assumption that higher outcomes are better (as in e.g. months of survival). Specifically, we examine the setting where a new OPM is supposed to ‘personalize’ an existing treatment policy by considering additional features. We characterize the scenarios where the introduction of a policy based on a prediction model is detrimental for patient outcomes. Section 3 presents the main results concerning OPMs that are harmful and self-fulfilling prophecies, and discusses the use of calibration as ‘canary in a coal mine’ to detect the aforementioned problems. We first show that even in a simple setup with a binary covariate, a non-trivial subset of OPMs yields harmful self-fulfilling prophecies. Next, perhaps surprisingly, we show that when an OPM is well calibrated on both 1) the historical data and 2) a validation study where the model is used for treatment decisions, the OPM is not useful for decision making. Based on our results, several common practices in building and deploying OPMs intended for decision making need revision: 1. Developing OPMs on observational data without regard of the historical treatment policy is potentially dangerous, because the change in treatment policy between pre- and post-deployment is what determines the effect of the model on patient outcomes. 2. Implementing a personalized outcome prediction model is not always beneficial, even if the model is very accurate. 3.

Monitoring discrimination prospectively after deployment will not determine whether the model is causing harm or not.

2. Notation and definitions

We assume a binary treatment T , a binary outcome Y and a binary feature $X \in \mathcal{X}$. We denote the outcome obtained with setting treatment T to t , conditional on X as $Y_t(X)$. An OPM is a function trained on historical data to predict the outcome of interest. We use $\pi_i(X)$ to denote a policy for assigning treatment, possibly conditional on X , with an index i to indicate what policy we are referring to. Throughout the paper π_0 will be used to indicate the *historic treatment policy* that was in place in the data in which the OPM was developed.

We assume the historical policy is *independent of X* , meaning that it is constant regardless of the value of X :

Definition 1 (Policy independent of X) We call a policy $\pi : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ independent of X if for all $x, x' \in \mathcal{X}$:

$$\pi(x) = \pi(x') \quad (1)$$

Next we define what it means to craft a policy based on an existing OPM. We will be concerned only with *threshold-based policies*, namely policies that assign treatment based on a threshold $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$. We focus on policies assigning treatment to patients only if they have a good enough expected outcome, i.e. an expected outcome above λ with the assumption that a higher outcome is preferable (e.g. months of survival).

Definition 2 (Policy informed by OPM)

Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an OPM and $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ a threshold. We call a policy informed by f a policy π_f defined as follows

$$\pi_f(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & f(x) > \lambda \\ 0 & f(x) \leq \lambda \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Such policies describe the post-deployment scenario, when the OPM influences treatment assignment. The same subscripts are employed for probabilities: $p_i(-)$ with $i \in \{0, f\}$ will denote a probability referring to the pre- or post-implementation distribution. Armed with this notation, we can present one of the key ideas of this paper, namely the special class of OPMs whose predictions are realized upon implementation.

Definition 3 (Self-fulfilling OPM) Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an OPM, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ a threshold and let π_f be the policy informed by f . Let $AUC(i)$ denote the AUC of this OPM on the historic policy ($i = 0$) or on the policy defined by f ($i = f$). We call the pair (f, λ) self-fulfilling if AUC remains the same or increases post-deployment, namely iff:

$$AUC(f) \geq AUC(0) \quad (3)$$

Finally, we specify what we mean with an OPM being harmful in comparison with the status quo.

Definition 4 (Harmful OPM) Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an OPM, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ a threshold and let π_f be the policy informed by f . We call f harmful for the group with $X = x$ if the outcome of the group¹ is worse under the new policy compared to the old policy, namely iff

$$\mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_f(x)} Y_T(x) < \mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_0(x)} Y_T(x) \quad (4)$$

When a policy informed by an OPM is both harmful and self-fulfilling we have a worst-case scenario where the new policy is causing harm to a subgroup but this is not detected by AUC.

1. Note that this is different from a model being marginally harmful, i.e. applying π_f leads to worse outcomes on average.

3. Results

We now move to the main results, whose proofs can be found in Appendix B. The setting where a new OPM is supposed to ‘personalize’ an already existing treatment policy by considering more features is encoded as follows: the new OPM considers a feature X that was previously ignored by the historical policy, specifically π_0 is independent of X . In addition, the new policy π_f is not constant. We state our main observation as an informal theorem.

Theorem 5 (Informally stated) *Let π_f be the policy informed by an OPM f using a threshold λ . Assume that: i) the historical policy π_0 is deterministic and independent of X and ii) the new policy π_f is not constant, i.e. not always equal to 1 or 0.*

Under these assumptions, a non-trivial subset of OPMs will demonstrate good post-deployment discrimination because they induce self-fulfilling prophecies, and at the same time harm patient outcomes when deployed.

The theorem is summarized with Figure 1. We proceed to characterize the contours of the subset of self-fulfilling and harmful OPMs.

Proposition 6 (Self-fulfilling) *Suppose the assumptions of Theorem 5 hold. Assume that the marginal distribution of X is constant: $p_i(X) = p(X)$ for $i \in \{0, f\}$. Furthermore assume that both the marginal and the conditional probabilities of Y given X (both pre- and post-deployment) are non-deterministic:*

$$0 < p_i(Y = 1|X = x), p(X = x) < 1, \forall x \in \mathcal{X} \quad (5)$$

Then the following two statements are true: i) if treatment effect is always positive, namely $\forall x \in \mathcal{X} : Y_1(x) - Y_0(x) \geq 0$, then (f, λ) is self-fulfilling; ii) if treatment effect is always negative, meaning $\forall x \in \mathcal{X} : Y_1(x) - Y_0(x) < 0$, then (f, λ) is not self-fulfilling.

Remark 7 *Observe that the threshold λ remains generic throughout the proof, so the result holds for any threshold satisfying the assumptions. Furthermore, it is also possible to formulate self-fulfilling in terms of expected outcomes alone, in which case one can get a proposition analogous to Proposition 6 but with an iff characterization. We expand on this in Appendix C.*

Now we know when OPMs are self-fulfilling and thus have good post-deployment discrimination, but can these self-fulfilling OPMs also be harmful? Proposition 8 indicates that they can:

Proposition 8 (Harmful)

Under the assumptions of Theorem 5, f is harmful for the group with $X = x$ iff

1. $\pi_0(x) = 1$ and $\pi_f(x) = 0$ and $Y_1(x) > Y_0(x)$ or
2. $\pi_0(x) = 0$ and $\pi_f(x) = 1$ and $Y_0(x) > Y_1(x)$

The conditions of this Proposition indicate that, as one would expect, removing the treatment from this group is harmful iff $Y_1(x) > Y_0(x)$, i.e. if the effect of the treatment was positive for this group. Conversely, adding treatment to group with $X = x$ is damaging iff $Y_1(x) < Y_0(x)$, meaning that the treatment decreases the outcome for the group. Taking together Proposition 6 and Proposition 8 we reach the perhaps surprising conclusion of Theorem 5: even in the simple setup of binary treatment and binary X , some OPMs are both self-fulfilling prophecies, and thus demonstrate good post-deployment discrimination, and harm a patient subgroup when deployed. We present an example based on realistic medical assumptions in Appendix A.

Given these results an important question is: how can a model be tested during deployment to verify that it is not causing harm? Since a self-fulfilling model (including a harmful one!) retains discrimination post deployment we need other metrics. Prediction models are typically validated in observational studies where treatment allocation is not randomized, which means that directly estimating causal effects such as $Y_t(X)$ is not possible. Another key metric of OPMs predicting the risk of an outcome is *calibration* (Alba et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2020; Van Calster et al., 2019). For the remainder of the section we examine calibration for OPMs predicting a binary outcome Y using the following definition:

Definition 9 Let $P(X, Y)$ be a joint distribution over features X and binary outcome Y , and $f : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ a prediction function. $f(x)$ is calibrated with respect to $P(X, Y)$ if, for all $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ in the range of f , $\mathbb{E}_{X, Y \sim P(X, Y)}[Y | f(X) = \alpha] = \alpha$.

We distinguish two distributions on which an OPM can be calibrated depending on the treatment policy indicated with $i \in \{0, f\}$ representing the distribution under the historical treatment policy and the deployment distribution:

$$p_i(Y = 1 | X) = \mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_i(X)} Y_T(X) \quad (6)$$

Theorem 5 states that harmful OPMs can have good pre- and post-deployment discrimination, but can they also have good calibration? It may seem reasonable to require that a model with good calibration on historical data should also have good calibration post-deployment. We define a treatment-blind OPM to *perfectly fit historical data* when it assumes the form

$$f(X) = \mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_0(X)} Y_T(X). \quad (7)$$

In what follows we show that, even with a binary covariate X , it may not be desirable for a model with such a perfect calibration pre-deployment to be also calibrated post-deployment.

Theorem 10 Let f be an OPM that perfectly fits historical data and π_f be non constant. Such OPM is calibrated on the deployment distribution iff for every $x \in \mathcal{X}$:

$$\pi_0(x) = \pi_f(x) \text{ or } Y_1(x) = Y_0(x) \quad (8)$$

Note that this entails that either the treatment policy does not change, or it changes where it is irrelevant because for that value of X the treatment effect is zero. Both cases imply the implementation of the OPM is inconsequential. This may seem surprising, but it boils down to the fact that a model that perfectly fits historical data is – by definition – calibrated on the historical distribution. Hence the model being calibrated both before and after deployment means the distribution has not changed, so the policy remains the same or the policy was changed where it is irrelevant (i.e. no treatment effect). So an OPM that is calibrated on the development cohort, which remains calibrated post deployment is not a useful OPM.

4. Related work

Previous work noted that prediction accuracy does not equal value for treatment decision making (Vickers and Elkin, 2006; Moons et al., 2015; van Amsterdam et al., 2022). Here we exactly characterize a set of prediction models that yield harmful self-fulfilling prophecies. The idea that model deployment changes the distribution and affects model performance is not new. Several authors noted that model performance may degrade over time due to the effect of deployment of the model (Lenert et al., 2019; Sperrin et al., 2019), but we study the case where model performance does *not* degrade but the implementation of it still caused harm. Perdomo et al. (2021) and Liley et al. (2021) study the setting of performing successive model updates, each time after deploying the previous model for decision making. Perdomo et al. (2021) study when over successive deployments model performance stabilizes or reaches optimality, and Liley et al. (2021) study both model stability and the effect of model deployment on outcomes. Our work may be seen as a special case of these works with only a single model deployment and no model update, but we add new insights as we describe exactly *when* a single model deployment leads to harm and good post-deployment discrimination. Several groups have studied out-of-distribution generalization and its connections to causality and invariance (Arjovsky et al., 2020; Wald et al., 2021; Puli et al., 2023) with the aim of removing a model’s dependency on *spurious correlations*. Again our work differs as we are interested in characterizing model performance following a very specific distribution change (a treatment policy change induced by a prediction model) that is particularly relevant in health care, and our main concern is the effect of this policy change on outcomes. Finally, current guidelines on prediction model validation and deployment focus on discrimination and calibration only, not on these newer invariance metrics (Moons et al., 2015; Kattan et al., 2016).

5. Discussion

We showed how OPMs can be harmful self-fulfilling prophecies, meaning they lead to patient harm when used for treatment decision making, but retain good discrimination after deployment. Moreover, we showed that when a model is well calibrated before and after deployment it is not useful for treatment decision making. These results cast doubt on the adequacy of current practice for the evaluation of predictive models post deployment, when these models are used for decision making.

Some limitations remain. We described the setting where treatments are prescribed to patients with a good predicted outcome, for example when treatments are burdensome and are deemed futile for patients with a bad expected outcome, or under resource scarcity. A different situation is when treatments are preferably given to patients with a bad predicted outcome, for example when prescribing cholesterol lowering medications to patients based on their risk of a heart attack. The extension of our results to those settings, as well as to other feature types, non-threshold based policies, or to a π_0 that is not independent of X or is non-deterministic, is left to future work.

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Appendix A. Hypothetical example of a harmful self-fulfilling prophecy

We now give a full-fledged hypothetical example based on realistic assumptions that would result in an OPM inducing a policy that is both harmful and self-fulfilling.

Consider the problem of selecting a subset of end-stage cancer patients for palliative radiotherapy. Such treatment has severe side-effects and thus domain experts advice to attempt to reduce over-treatment in the population of cancer patients. To comply with this advice, a medical center needs to decide which patients will not be eligible anymore for the therapy.

The medical center decides to give the therapy to patients with the longest expected overall survival, under the assumption that these patients would be those for whom the side-effects are justifiable. To support this policy, researchers built an OPM to predict months of overall survival based on pre-treatment tumor growth rate using historical patient records from the medical center. Fast-growing tumors are more aggressive so these patients have a shorter survival overall. The medical center decides to use this model to allocate the therapy and tests the model’s discrimination post deployment. Based on this we have the following facts:

1. $X = 1$: fast growing tumor, $X = 0$: slow-growing tumor;
2. $\pi_0(X) = 1$, the historical policy was treating everyone;
3. $\delta := Y_0(X = 0) - Y_0(X = 1) > 0$, with radiotherapy, patients with fast growing tumors live shorter, where we assume δ to be small on a relevant scale of overall survival.

A model with a good fit to the data will predict that patients with slow-growing tumors have a higher survival time. We also assume that the new policy is non-constant and favors those with highest predicted outcome, which means that the new policy will be ‘treat patients with slow growing tumors but not those with fast growing tumors’:

$$\pi_f(X) = 1 - X$$

However, it is well known that fast-growing tumors respond better to radiotherapy than slow growing tumors (Breur, 1966). Based on this we add the following two assumptions:

1. $Y_0(X = 0) - Y_1(X = 0) = 0$, radiotherapy is not effective against slow growing tumors;
2. $\epsilon := Y_0(X = 1) - Y_1(X = 1) < 0$, radiotherapy *is* effective for fast growing tumors.

This means that the antecedent of Proposition 6 is satisfied, meaning that f yields a self-fulfilling prophecy in combination with any threshold λ such that the resulting policy is non-constant. Removing the therapy from the group $X = 1$ will worsen their outcomes by ϵ , separating the two groups even more and resulting in higher AUC post-deployment.

Moreover, according to the first case of Proposition 8, the OPM is harmful because the new treatment policy leads to worse outcomes for the group with fast growing tumors ($X = 1$). So the OPM-based policy treats exactly the wrong patients: those who do not benefit from treatment still receive it, those who would benefit from treatment do not, but paradoxically it has good discrimination before and after deployment.

Appendix B. Proofs of main results

Given that we assumed binary T and X , we can write the expected value of the outcome conditional on these two variables with four parameters without making parametric assumptions, marginalizing over other variables different than X and T . For ease of interpretation of our results we write the expected value as a sum:

$$\mathbb{E}Y(T = t, X = x) = \alpha + \beta_x x + \beta_t t + \beta_{xt} xt \tag{9}$$

Note that this is not an assumption on the generating process of the outcome Y , which could have arbitrary form, it is only a formal device to represent the four outcomes of interest, one for each value of X and T .

B.1. Proof of Proposition 6.

Proof

First we give some elementary definitions and equalities. Define

$$\mu_i(x) = p_i(Y = 1|X = x) = (1 - \pi_i(x))Y_0(x) + \pi_i(x)Y_1(x) \quad (10)$$

So by the law of total probability we can write

$$p_i(Y = 1) = p_i(X = 0)\mu_i(0) + p_i(X = 1)\mu_i(1) \quad (11)$$

By Bayes rule we have:

$$p_i(X = x|Y = y) = \frac{p_i(Y = y|X = x)p(X = x)}{p_i(Y = y)} \quad (12)$$

Filling in the definition of $\mu_i(x)$ into 12 using the assumption that $p_i(X = x) = p(X = x)$ we have in particular:

$$p_i(X = x|Y = 1) = \frac{\mu_i(x)p(X = x)}{p_i(Y = 1)} \quad (13)$$

ROC-curves are created by transforming a continuous-valued function to a binary prediction based on a varying *threshold* τ and calculating the *sensitivity* and *specificity* for each value of τ :

$$\text{sensitivity} = p(f(X) \geq \tau|Y = 1) \quad (14)$$

$$\text{specificity} = p(f(X) < \tau|Y = 0) \quad (15)$$

For each possible threshold, all predictions under the threshold are labeled *negative* and all predictions greater or equal to the threshold *positive*. In the case of a binary X , $f(X)$ only takes two unique values so the ROC-curve is given by just three points:

1. sensitivity = 1, specificity = 0 ($\tau = -\infty$)
2. sensitivity = 0, specificity = 1 ($\tau = +\infty$)
3. sensitivity = sens, specificity = spec ($\tau = \max_X f(X)$)

See Figure 2. We can directly calculate the AUC by dividing the area under the ROC-curve in two adjacent non-overlapping triangles. This gives us the following expression for the AUC (see also [Muschelli \(2020\)](#)):

$$\text{AUC} = \frac{1}{2}\text{sens} + \frac{1}{2}\text{spec} \quad (16)$$

In this binary case, the area-under the ROC curve is thus determined by a single point denoted as (spec,sens). A pair (f, λ) is self-fulfilling when:

$$\text{AUC}(f) - \text{AUC}(0) = \frac{1}{2}(\text{sens}_f + \text{spec}_f - \text{sens}_0 - \text{spec}_0) \geq 0 \quad (17)$$

We structure the proof by first creating an enumeration over all possible scenarios. We assumed π_f is non-constant, which implies that f varies with X . Since X is binary, it must be that either $f(0) > f(1)$ or $f(1) > f(0)$. These cases are equivalent under relabeling of X so without loss of generality we proceed assuming that $f(0) > f(1)$ is the case. Since π_f is not constant but π_0 is, it must be that either the treatment policy changes for $X = 0$ but remains the same for $X = 1$, or vice versa. This in turn implies that either $\mu_f(0) = \mu_0(0)$ or $\mu_f(1) = \mu_0(1)$.

To provide a proof for the theorem, we enumerate all the subcases based on two factors:

 Figure 2: AUC for a binary predictor X

1. for which group does the policy change ($X = 0$ or $X = 1$)?
2. for the group with the policy change, does the outcome under the new policy remain the same (the policy is inconsequential as the treatment effect is zero), increase (the policy leads to better outcomes) or decreases (the policy is harmful)

This leads to the following 6 cases:

- policy change for which X ?

0. $\pi_f(0) \neq \pi_0(0)$

effect of policy change:

- =: $\mu_f(0) = \mu_0(0), \mu_f(1) = \mu_0(1)$
- <: $\mu_f(0) < \mu_0(0), \mu_f(1) = \mu_0(1)$
- >: $\mu_f(0) > \mu_0(0), \mu_f(1) = \mu_0(1)$

1. $\pi_f(1) \neq \pi_0(1)$

effect of policy change:

- =: $\mu_f(0) = \mu_0(0), \mu_f(1) = \mu_0(1)$
- <: $\mu_f(0) = \mu_0(0), \mu_f(1) < \mu_0(1)$
- >: $\mu_f(0) = \mu_0(0), \mu_f(1) > \mu_0(1)$

These 6 combinations cover all possibilities. Since we have that $f(0) > f(1)$, by assumption of a non-deterministic $\pi_f(x) = I_{f(x) > \lambda}$ it must be that for all subcases $\pi_f(0) = 1$ and $\pi_f(1) = 0$. Each of these cases have implications for π_0 and, depending on which policy changes, $Y_1(0) - Y_0(0)$ or $Y_1(1) - Y_0(1)$. For instance case $(0, >)$ specifies that $\pi_f(0) \neq \pi_0(0)$ so it follows that $\pi_0 = 0$. And because $Y_1(0) = \mu_f(0) > \mu_0(0) = Y_0(0)$ it must be that $Y_1(0) - Y_0(0) > 0$, meaning that the treatment is beneficial for the group with $X = 0$.

In the two cases where the outcomes do not change ($(0, =)$ and $(1, =)$), (f, λ) is trivially self-fulfilling as nothing changes in the distribution of X, Y so the sensitivity and specificity remain the same.

We first prove self-fulfillingness in cases $(0, >)$ and $(0, <)$:

Case $(0, >)$ and $(0, <)$ We first address case $(0, >)$, which gives us this information:

- $\pi_f(0) \neq \pi_0(0)$
- $\mu_f(0) > \mu_0(0)$
- $\mu_f(1) = \mu_0(1)$

Since $f(0) > f(1)$ we get these sensitivity and specificity:

$$\text{sens}_i = p_i(f(X) \geq \max(f)|Y = 1) = p_i(X = 0|Y = 1) \quad (18)$$

$$\text{spec}_i = p_i(f(X) < \max(f)|Y = 0) = p_i(X = 1|Y = 0) \quad (19)$$

with $i \in \{0, f\}$. Plugging this into 17 yields:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{AUC}(f) - \text{AUC}(0) &= \frac{1}{2}(p_f(X = 0|Y = 1) - p_0(X = 0|Y = 1) \\ &\quad + p_f(X = 1|Y = 0) - p_0(X = 0|Y = 0)) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(\mu_f(0) \frac{p(X = 0)}{p_f(Y = 1)} - \mu_0(0) \frac{p(X = 0)}{p_0(Y = 1)} \\ &\quad + (1 - \mu_f(1)) \frac{p(X = 1)}{p_f(Y = 0)} - (1 - \mu_0(1)) \frac{p(X = 1)}{p_0(Y = 0)}) \end{aligned}$$

where the first equality is by substitution and rearrangement, and the second by Bayes rule. We can determine the sign of this difference based on the sign of two terms:

$$= \frac{1}{2}(p(X = 0) \left(\frac{\mu_f(0)}{p_f(Y = 1)} - \frac{\mu_0(0)}{p_0(Y = 1)} \right) \quad (20)$$

$$+ p(X = 1) \left(\frac{1 - \mu_f(1)}{p_f(Y = 0)} - \frac{1 - \mu_0(1)}{p_0(Y = 0)} \right)) \quad (21)$$

We write the difference between pre- and post-deployment expected outcome for the group $X = 0$ as

$$\delta := \mu_f(0) - \mu_0(0) \quad (22)$$

This gives us

$$p_f(Y = 1) = p(X = 1)\mu_f(1) + p(X = 0)\mu_f(0) \quad (23)$$

$$= p(X = 1)\mu_0(1) + p(X = 0)(\mu_0(0) + \delta) \quad (24)$$

$$= p_0(Y = 1) + p(X = 0)\delta \quad (25)$$

where the first step is the law of total probability, the second by the definition of δ and the case information $\mu_f(1) = \mu_0(1)$, and finally again using the law of total probability. Furthermore

$$p_f(Y = 0) = 1 - p_f(Y = 1) \quad (26)$$

$$= 1 - p_0(Y = 1) - p(X = 0)\delta \quad (27)$$

$$= p_0(Y = 0) - p(X = 0)\delta \quad (28)$$

where the second step is by our previous calculation and the other two just the property of binary outcomes. We can now determine the signs of the two terms in 20.

$$\text{sign}\left[\frac{\mu_f(0)}{p_f(Y=1)} - \frac{\mu_0(0)}{p_0(Y=1)}\right] = \text{sign}\left[\frac{\mu_f(0)p_0(Y=1) - \mu_0(0)p_f(Y=1)}{p_f(Y=1)p_0(Y=1)}\right] \quad (29)$$

$$= \text{sign}[\mu_f(0)p_0(Y=1) - \mu_0(0)p_f(Y=1)] \quad (30)$$

The first equality is cross-multiplying, the second equality is because the product of two probabilities (which are positive by assumption) is always a positive number.

Filling in the definition of δ :

$$\text{sign}\left[\frac{\mu_f(0)}{p_f(Y=1)} - \frac{\mu_0(0)}{p_0(Y=1)}\right] \quad (31)$$

$$= \text{sign}[(\mu_0(0) + \delta)p_0(Y=1) - \mu_0(0)(p_0(Y=1) + p(X=0)\delta)] \quad (32)$$

$$= \text{sign}[\delta p_0(Y=1) - \mu_0(0)p(X=0)\delta] \quad (33)$$

$$= \text{sign}[\delta(p_0(Y=1) - \mu_0(0)p(X=0))] \quad (34)$$

$$= \text{sign}[\delta\mu_0(1)p(X=1)] \quad (35)$$

$$= \text{sign}[\delta] \quad (36)$$

In the second equality we remove canceling terms. In the third equality we pull out δ . In the fourth equality we use the expansion of $p_0(Y=1) = p(X=0)\mu_0(0) + p(X=1)\mu_0(1)$, and for the final equation we note again that $\mu_0(1)$ and $p(X=1)$ are positive probabilities so the sign is determined by the sign of δ .

Now for the second term of 20:

$$\text{sign}\left[\frac{1 - \mu_f(1)}{p_f(Y=0)} - \frac{1 - \mu_0(1)}{p_0(Y=0)}\right] = \text{sign}\left[\frac{1 - \mu_0(1)}{p_f(Y=0)} - \frac{1 - \mu_0(1)}{p_0(Y=0)}\right] \quad (37)$$

$$= \text{sign}\left[(1 - \mu_0(1))\left(\frac{1}{p_f(Y=0)} - \frac{1}{p_0(Y=0)}\right)\right] \quad (38)$$

$$= \text{sign}\left[\frac{1}{p_f(Y=0)} - \frac{1}{p_0(Y=0)}\right] \quad (39)$$

$$= \text{sign}\left[\frac{p_0(Y=0) - p_f(Y=0)}{p_f(Y=0)p_0(Y=0)}\right] \quad (40)$$

$$= \text{sign}[p_0(Y=0) - p_f(Y=0)] \quad (41)$$

$$= \text{sign}[p_0(Y=0) - p_0(Y=0) + p(X=0)\delta] \quad (42)$$

$$= \text{sign}[p(X=0)\delta] \quad (43)$$

$$= \text{sign}[\delta] \quad (44)$$

The first equality uses the case assumption that $\mu_f(1) = \mu_0(1)$. The second equality pulls out the common term $(1 - \mu_0(1))$. The third equality follows because $0 < \mu_0(1) < 1$. The fourth and fifth equality are cross-multiplying and again using the positive probability property. In the sixth equality we substitute in the definition of δ . The seventh equality removes the canceling terms, and the final equality again relies on that $0 < p(X=0)$.

So both terms in 20 have the sign of δ . In subcase $(0, >)$ δ has positive sign, so

$$\text{AUC}(f) - \text{AUC}(0) > 0$$

and (f, λ) is self-fulfilling.

Immediately it is clear that in subcase $(0, <)$, (f, λ) is not self-fulfilling, as subcase $(0, <)$ equals subcase $(0, >)$ in all respects except that instead it has a negative sign for δ .

Case (1, >) and (1, <) We first address case (1, >), which gives us this information:

- $\pi_f(1) \neq \pi_0(1)$
- $\mu_f(0) = \mu_0(0)$
- $\mu_f(1) > \mu_0(1)$

Again we write the difference between pre- and post-deployment expected outcome as δ , this time for the group $X = 1$:

$$\delta := \mu_f(1) - \mu_0(1) \quad (45)$$

This gives us

$$p_f(Y = 1) = p(X = 1)\mu_f(1) + p(X = 0)\mu_f(0) \quad (46)$$

$$= p(X = 1)(\mu_0(1) + \delta) + p(X = 0)\mu_0(0) \quad (47)$$

$$= p_0(Y = 1) + p(X = 1)\delta \quad (48)$$

where the first step is the law of total probability, the second by the definition of δ and the case information $\mu_f(0) = \mu_0(0)$, and finally again using the law of total probability. Furthermore

$$p_f(Y = 0) = 1 - p_f(Y = 1) \quad (49)$$

$$= 1 - p_0(Y = 1) - p(X = 1)\delta \quad (50)$$

$$= p_0(Y = 0) - p(X = 1)\delta \quad (51)$$

where the second step is by our previous calculation and the other two just the property of binary outcomes. We can now determine the signs of the two terms in 20.

The first two steps for the first are the same as in the case (0, >) (see Equation 29), after these steps we substitute in the new definition of δ :

$$\text{sign}\left[\frac{\mu_f(0)}{p_f(Y = 1)} - \frac{\mu_0(0)}{p_0(Y = 1)}\right] \quad (52)$$

$$= \text{sign}[\mu_f(0)p_0(Y = 1) - \mu_0(0)p_f(Y = 1)] \quad (53)$$

$$= \text{sign}[\mu_0(0)p_0(Y = 1) - \mu_0(0)(p_0(Y = 1) + p(X = 1)\delta)] \quad (54)$$

$$= \text{sign}[-\mu_0(0)p(X = 0)\delta] \quad (55)$$

$$= \text{sign}[-\delta] \quad (56)$$

In the third equality we remove canceling terms. For the final equation we note again that $\mu_0(0)$ and $p(X = 0)$ are positive probabilities so the sign is determined by the sign of δ .

Now for the second term of 20:

subcase	π_0	$\pi_f(0)$	$\pi_f(1)$	$Y_1(0) - Y_0(0)$	$Y_1(1) - Y_1(1)$	self-fulfilling
0 =	0	1	0	0		yes
0 <	0	1	0	-		no
0 >	0	1	0	+		yes
1 =	1	1	0		0	yes
1 <	1	1	0		+	yes
1 >	1	1	0		-	no

Table 1: all possible subcases. The first column indicates for which value of X the treatment policy changes. The second column indicates whether this change improves outcomes for that group ($>$), reduces outcomes ($<$) or is irrelevant ($=$). $+/-$ indicates the sign of the subgroup treatment effect $Y_1(x) - Y_0(x)$;

$$\text{sign}\left[\frac{1 - \mu_f(1)}{p_f(Y=0)} - \frac{1 - \mu_0(1)}{p_0(Y=0)}\right] \quad (57)$$

$$= \text{sign}\left[\frac{(1 - \mu_f(1))p_0(Y=0) - (1 - \mu_0(1))p_f(Y=0)}{p_f(Y=0)p_0(Y=0)}\right] \quad (58)$$

$$= \text{sign}\left[(1 - \mu_f(1))p_0(Y=0) - (1 - \mu_0(1))p_f(Y=0)\right] \quad (59)$$

$$= \text{sign}\left[(1 - (\mu_0(1) + \delta))p_0(Y=0) + (1 - \mu_0(1))(p_0(Y=0) - p(X=1)\delta)\right] \quad (60)$$

$$= \text{sign}\left[-\delta p_0(Y=0) - (1 - \mu_0(1))(-p(X=1)\delta)\right] \quad (61)$$

$$= \text{sign}\left[-\delta(p_0(Y=0) - (1 - \mu_0(1))p(X=1))\right] \quad (62)$$

$$= \text{sign}\left[-\delta((1 - \mu_0(0))p(X=0))\right] \quad (63)$$

$$= \text{sign}\left[-\delta\right] \quad (64)$$

The first equality uses cross-multiplication to gather the sum. The second equality follows because we're dividing by a positive number. The third equality is filling in the definition on δ . The fourth equality removes canceling terms. The fifth equality factors out $-\delta$. The seventh equality is by the law of total probability.

So both terms in 20 have the sign of $-\delta$. In subcase $(1, >)$ δ has positive sign, so

$$\text{AUC}(f) - \text{AUC}(0) < 0$$

and (f, λ) is not self-fulfilling.

Immediately it is clear that in subcase $(1, <)$, (f, λ) is self-fulfilling, as subcase $(1, <)$ equals subcase $(1, >)$ in all respects except that instead it has a negative sign for δ .

Enumerating all the cases As said, in the two cases where the outcomes do not change ($(0, =)$, $(1, =)$), (f, λ) is trivially self-fulfilling.

Putting all the pieces of information for all subcases together in Table 1 we see that when $Y_1(x) - Y_0(x) \geq 0$ (the treatment effect is never negative), (f, λ) is self-fulfilling. Also, when $Y_1(x) - Y_0(x) < 0$ (the treatment is always negative), (f, λ) is never self-fulfilling. These observations conclude the proof. ■

B.2. Proof of Proposition 8.

Proof A treatment is harmful for the group with $X = x'$ iff $\mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_f(x')} Y_t(x') < \mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_0(x')} Y_t(x')$. The proof continues as a case distinction depending on the value of x' .

Case $x' = 1$. For $x' = 1$ the definition of harmful translates to

$$(\pi_f(1) - \pi_0(1))(\beta_t + \beta_{xt}) < 0 \quad (65)$$

We consider the possible values of π_f and π_0 in subcases. Note that if $\pi_f(1) = \pi_0(1)$ the above inequality cannot hold since all terms cancel out and the treatment cannot be harmful (because nothing changes for group $X = 1$), so we only consider subcases where these two differ.

Subcase 1. We have $\pi_f(1) = 0, \pi_f(0) = 1$ and $\pi_0(x) = 1$. In this scenario, we were treating everyone and with the new policy we withhold treatment from group $X = 1$. In this case statement 65 specializes to $\beta_t + \beta_{xt} > 0$, meaning that treatment was beneficial and removing it will do damage to group $X = 1$.

Subcase 2. We have $\pi_f(1) = 1, \pi_f(0) = 0$ and $\pi_0(x) = 0$. In this scenario, we were treating nobody and with the new policy we introduce treatment for group $X = 1$. In this case statement 65 specializes to $\beta_t + \beta_{xt} < 0$, meaning that treatment is harmful and adding it damages group $X = 1$.

Case $x' = 0$. For $x' = 0$ the definition of harmful translates to

$$(\pi_f(0) - \pi_0(0))\beta_t < 0 \quad (66)$$

Again if $\pi_f(0) = \pi_0(0)$ the above inequality cannot hold since all terms cancel out and the treatment cannot be harmful (because nothing changes for group $X = 0$), so we only consider subcases where these two differ.

Subcase 1. We have $\pi_f(1) = 0, \pi_f(0) = 1$ and $\pi_0(x) = 0$. In this scenario, we were treating nobody and with the new policy we introduce treatment from group $X = 0$. In this case the statement 66 specializes to $\beta_t < 0$, which is what we intended to prove. This means the treatment effect is negative and thus group $X = 0$ is damaged.

Subcase 2. We have $\pi_f(1) = 1, \pi_f(0) = 0$ and $\pi_0(x) = 1$. In this circumstance statement 66 specializes to $\beta_t > 0$. ■

B.3. Proof of Theorem 10.

By assumption f perfectly fits the historical data, so:

$$f(X = x) = \mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_0(x)} Y_T(x) = p_0(Y = 1 | X = x).$$

We now prove that f is calibrated on the deployment distribution generated by π_f iff for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$:

$$\pi_0(x) = \pi_f(x) \text{ or } Y_1(x) = Y_0(x) \quad (67)$$

Proof As a shorthand define:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_i(x) &:= \mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_i(x)} Y_T(x) \\ &= (1 - \pi_i(x))Y_0(x) + \pi_i(x)Y_1(x). \end{aligned}$$

f perfectly fits the historical data so:

$$f(X = x) = \mu_0(x), \forall x \in \mathcal{X}. \quad (68)$$

f is calibrated on the deployment distribution when for all $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ in the range of f , $\mathbb{E}_{X, Y \sim P_f(X, Y)}[Y | f(X) = \alpha] = \alpha$. We first show that this holds iff for every $x \in \mathcal{X}$, $f(x) = \mu_f(x)$. For the left-to-right, consider a generic x and say $f(x) = \alpha$. By the definition of calibration we can rewrite the expected outcome in the post-deployment distribution for the subset of X in the pre-image of α under f as follows: $\mathbb{E}_{x \in f^{-1}(\alpha)} \mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_f(x)} Y_T(x) = \alpha = f(x)$. This gives us the following derivation

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= \alpha \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{x \in f^{-1}(\alpha)} \mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_f(x)} Y_T(x) \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{x \in f^{-1}(\alpha)} \mu_f(x) \\ &= \mu_f(x) \end{aligned}$$

where the last step is given by the fact that since π_f is non constant f must be injective on the binary covariate X , thus the pre-image contains only x .

For the right-to-left, let α be in the image of f and consider $\mathbb{E}_{X, Y \sim P_f(X, Y)}[Y | f(X) = \alpha]$. Again we rewrite this as the expected outcome in the pre-image of α :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}_{x \in f^{-1}(\alpha)} \mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_f(x)} Y_T(x) &= \mathbb{E}_{x \in f^{-1}(\alpha)} \mu_f(x) \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{x \in f^{-1}(\alpha)} f(x) \\ &= \alpha \end{aligned}$$

Where the first equality is by definition and the second by the assumption $f(x) = \mu_f(x)$. This concludes that $x \in \mathcal{X}$, $f(x) = \mu_f(x)$, and, because f fits historical data, $x \in \mathcal{X}$, $\mu_0(x) = \mu_f(x)$ follows.

Looking at the difference between $\mu_0(x)$ and $\mu_f(x)$ we see that:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_f(x) - \mu_0(x) &= \\ &= ((1 - \pi_f(x))Y_0(x) + \pi_f(x)Y_1(x)) - \\ &= ((1 - \pi_0(x))Y_0(x) + \pi_0(x)Y_1(x)) \\ &= (\pi_f(x) - \pi_0(x)) (Y_1(x) - Y_0(x)) \end{aligned}$$

Hence the difference $\mu_f(x) - \mu_0(x)$ is zero iff at least one of the last two terms is zero. This means that f is calibrated on the deployment distribution iff for every x either $\pi_f(x) = \pi_0(x)$ or $Y_1(x) = Y_0(x)$ ■

Appendix C. Self-fulfilling in terms of expected outcomes

We begin by rephrasing the definition of self-fulfilling.

Definition 11 (Self-fulfilling OPM) *Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an OPM, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ a threshold and let π_f be the policy informed by f . We call (f, λ) self-fulfilling for the pair $x, x' \in \mathcal{X}$ if the ranking of expected values of outcomes predicted by f materializes after the implementation of the new policy, namely iff:*

$$f(x) < f(x') \Rightarrow \mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_f(x)} Y_T(x) < \mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_f(x')} Y_T(x') \quad (69)$$

Crucially, a model that is self-fulfilling for all pairs $(x, x') \in \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X}$ will tend to have good discrimination post-deployment, since the post-deployment data distribution reflects the ranking predicted by the model. We now prove an iff characterization of self-fulfilling analogous to Proposition 6.

Proposition 12 (Self-fulfilling)

Under the assumptions of Theorem 5 plus the fact that f perfectly fits historical data, (f, λ) is self-fulfilling for the pair (x, x') , with $x \neq x'$, iff $Y_0(x) < Y_1(x')$.

Thus for the OPM to be self-fulfilling on the pair (x, x') , $x \neq x'$, with threshold λ , the outcome of the group $X = x$ (the one that is worse off in the historical data) *without treatment* must be worse than the outcome of group $X = x'$ *with treatment*.

Proof As X is binary, the statement is equivalent to the following: f is self-fulfilling for pair $(1,0)$ iff $\beta_t > \beta_x$ and for the pair $(0,1)$ iff $\beta_{xt} + \beta_t + \beta_x > 0$. We start by proving both implications from right to left. What needs to be proven is statement 69. Suppose the antecedent $f(x) < f(x')$ is the case: since f fits historical data this means that we have an imbalance of outcomes when treatment is assigned following π_0 :

$$\mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_0(x)} Y_t(x) < \mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_0(x')} Y_t(x') \quad (70)$$

The proof proceeds as a case distinction depending on which of the two groups is worse off.

Case 1. Let us begin with $x = 1$ and $x' = 0$, hence the group with $X = 1$ is worse off. For this pair we have the additional assumption $\beta_t > \beta_x$ given by the right-to-left direction of the proof. Due to the outcome definition, the inequality of the antecedent 70 simplifies to

$$\pi_0(1)\beta_{xt} + \beta_t(\pi_0(1) - \pi_0(0)) + \beta_x < 0$$

Since the historical policy is independent of X , we know $\pi_0(1)$ and $\pi_0(0)$ will be the same, so we can further simplify this expression to get

$$\pi_0(1)\beta_{xt} + \beta_x < 0 \quad (71)$$

What remains to show is the consequent of the self-fulfilling definition, namely

$$\mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_f(x)} Y_t(x) < \mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_f(x')} Y_t(x') \quad (72)$$

Applying the substitution $x = 1$ and $x' = 0$ and using the same reasoning as for 70 this inequality reduces to

$$\pi_f(1)\beta_{xt} + \beta_t(\pi_f(1) - \pi_f(0)) + \beta_x < 0 \quad (73)$$

The proof proceeds as a further case distinction based on the values of $\pi_f(x)$. Since we have assumed $\pi_f(x)$ to be deterministic and not constant, one of two cases must occur, either $\pi_f(1) = 1, \pi_f(0) = 0$ or $\pi_f(1) = 0, \pi_f(0) = 1$.

Sub-case 1: $\pi_f(1) = 1, \pi_f(0) = 0$. By the definition of π_f this case entails that $f(1) > \lambda$ and $f(0) \leq \lambda$, which is in conflict with our assumptions. The rationale is that if the expected outcome of group $X = 1$ is above λ and the expected outcome of group $X = 0$ is $\leq \lambda$, then the outcome of group 1 is the largest, which violates assumption 70 under the substitution $x = 1$ and $x' = 0$.

Sub-case 2: $\pi_f(1) = 0, \pi_f(0) = 1$. Inequality 73 simplifies to $-\beta_t + \beta_x < 0$. But this is equivalent to $\beta_t > \beta_x$, which we have assumed to be the case for this pair. This concludes the proof for the case $x = 1$ and $x' = 0$.

Case 2. We now consider the other case where $x = 0$ and $x' = 1$, hence group with $X = 0$ is worse off according to the assumption $f(x) < f(x')$. For this pair we have the additional assumption $\beta_{xt} + \beta_t + \beta_x > 0$. Spelling out equation 70 for this case we obtain

$$\pi_0(1)\beta_{xt} + \beta_x > 0 \quad (74)$$

which is the same as equation 71 but with a flipped inequality. Similarly, what we need to show is

$$\pi_f(1)\beta_{xt} + \beta_t(\pi_f(1) - \pi_f(0)) + \beta_x > 0 \quad (75)$$

which is the same as equation 73 but with a flipped sign. This arm of the proof also continues with a distinction on the values of π_f .

Sub-case 1: $\pi_f(1) = 1, \pi_f(0) = 0$. In this scenario what needs to be proven (equation 75) specializes to $\beta_{xt} + \beta_t + \beta_x > 0$. This was the assumption for this case, so we can conclude this holds.

Sub-case 2: $\pi_f(1) = 0, \pi_f(0) = 1$. In this case by the definition of π_f we have that $f(0) > \lambda$ and $f(1) \leq \lambda$, which is in conflict with the case under consideration, i.e. $f(0) < f(1)$. Hence, this case cannot occur.

These case distinctions complete the right-to-left part of the proof. For the other direction(s), we assume in turn that first $\beta_t > \beta_x$ and then that $\beta_{xt} + \beta_t + \beta_x > 0$ is violated. In each of the two cases, we find a counterexample to the Definition 11 for the corresponding pair.

Case 1. In the scenario where $x = 1$ and $x' = 0$, consider a counterexample violating $\beta_t > \beta_x$, e.g. the one consisting of the following coefficients: $\beta_{xt} = 2, \beta_t = \beta_x = -1, \pi_0(x) = 0$. This example fulfills the antecedent of the self-fulfilling condition (equation 71) but because it violates $\beta_t > \beta_x$ it does not satisfy the consequent and is therefore a counterexample to Definition 11.

Case 2. In the scenario $x = 0$ and $x' = 1$, consider a counterexample violating $\beta_{xt} + \beta_t + \beta_x > 0$, for instance the one consisting of the following coefficients: $\beta_{xt} = 2, \beta_t = \beta_x = -1, \pi_0(x) = 1$. This example fulfills the antecedent of the self-fulfilling condition (equation 74) but because it violates $\beta_{xt} + \beta_t + \beta_x > 0$ it does not satisfy the consequent and is therefore a counterexample to Definition 11.

This concludes the left-to-right direction(s) and the proof altogether. ■

C.1. Example of harmful and self-fulfilling in the expected outcome version

Finally, we now give a full-fledged hypothetical example based on realistic assumptions that would result in an OPM inducing a policy that is both harmful and self-fulfilling in the expected outcome version.

Consider the problem of selecting a subset of end-stage cancer patients for proton therapy. Proton therapy is a relatively new form of radiotherapy with less side-effects than standard radiotherapy but it is very expensive. A medical center builds a new proton therapy facility and needs to decide what patients will be eligible as it is financially impossible to give the new therapy to all patients. Because the effect of proton-therapy may take weeks to become apparent, the medical center decides to give the therapy to patients with the longest expected overall survival under the assumption that these patients would benefit the most. To support this policy, researchers built an OPM to predict months of overall survival based on pre-treatment tumor growth rate using historical patient records from the medical center. Fast-growing tumors are more aggressive so without proton therapy, these patients have a shorter survival. The medical center decides to use this model to allocate proton therapy and tests the model's discrimination post deployment. Based on this we have the following facts:

1. $X = 1$: fast growing tumor, $X = 0$: slow-growing tumor;
2. $\pi_0(X) = 0$, the historical policy was treating no-one;
3. $\delta := Y_0(X = 0) - Y_0(X = 1) > 0$, without proton-therapy, patients with fast growing tumors live shorter, where we assume δ to be substantial on a relevant scale of overall survival.

Furthermore we will stipulate the assumptions of Theorem 5 to hold and the OPM perfectly fits the data:

$$f(X) = \mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_0(X)} Y_T(X) = Y_0(X)$$

In particular, this model will predict that patients with slow-growing tumors have a higher survival time. We also assume that the new policy is non-constant, which means that the new policy will be 'treat patients with slow growing tumors but not those with fast growing tumors':

$$\pi_f(X) = 1 - X$$

However, it is well known that fast-growing tumors respond better to radiotherapy than slow growing tumors (Breur, 1966), so it is highly likely that fast-growing tumors respond better to proton therapy as well. Based on this we add the following two assumptions:

1. $\epsilon := Y_0(X = 0) - Y_1(X = 0) > 0$, proton therapy is not effective against slow growing tumors, and due to the rare-but-not-absent side effects, proton therapy actually reduces overall survival by a small amount for this group of patients;
2. $Y_0(X = 1) - Y_1(X = 1) < 0$, proton therapy *is* effective for fast growing tumors.

We assumed δ to be substantial and ϵ to be small so $\delta > \epsilon > 0$, meaning that:

$$\begin{aligned} Y_0(1) &= Y_0(0) - \delta \\ &= Y_1(0) + \epsilon - \delta \\ &< Y_1(0) \end{aligned}$$

Thus the example satisfies the criteria of Proposition 12 as $f(1) < f(0)$ and $Y_0(1) < Y_1(0)$, meaning that f yields a self-fulfilling prophecy in combination with any threshold λ such that the resulting policy is non-constant. We can also explicitly calculate the post-deployment outcomes to see that f yields a self-fulfilling prophecy:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_f(X)} Y_T(X) &= XY_0(X) + (1 - X)Y_1(X) \\ &\implies \\ \mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_f(1)} Y_T(1) &= Y_0(1) < Y_1(0) = \mathbb{E}_{T \sim \pi_f(0)} Y_T(0) \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, according to Proposition 8 the OPM is harmful because the new treatment policy leads to worse outcomes for the group with slow growing tumors ($X = 0$). In addition to this OPM being harmful for the slow growing group, it is also clearly suboptimal as patients with fast growing tumors are not getting proton therapy, whereas it would have been beneficial to them as $Y_1(1) > Y_0(1)$. So the OPM-based policy treats exactly the wrong patients: those who are harmed by treatment receive it, those who would benefit from treatment do not, but paradoxically it has good discrimination before and after deployment.